

Prenatal Diagnosis of Fetal Anomalies by Ultrasonography & MRI: A Pictorial PresentationParesh Bhowmik¹, Janame Jeyan R²¹Senior Resident, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Agartala Government Medical College & GBPH, Agartala²Postgraduate Trainee, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Agartala Government Medical College & GBPH, Agartala

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Ultrasonography (USG) is commonly employed for assessing fetal development during pregnancy. However, fetal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has emerged as a valuable tool to complement USG by confirming or ruling out suspected abnormalities and uncovering additional issues, thus enhancing perinatal care and altering pregnancy outcomes. Recent advancements in ultrafast MRI sequences have significantly improved its diagnostic capabilities. This pictorial essay showcases a range of structural anomalies affecting various systems such as the central nervous system, thorax, genitourinary tract, gastrointestinal tract, and other miscellaneous anomalies. Additionally, anomalies in twin pregnancies and placental abnormalities are also explored in this comprehensive review.

Keywords: Congenital anomalies; fetal magnetic resonance imaging; ultrasonography.

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Introduction

Since the late 1950s, ultrasonography (USG) has been a standard tool in obstetrics and gynaecology, yet its limitations such as small field of view and operator dependency have necessitated additional imaging modalities, particularly in cases involving oligohydramnios or obese patients.[1] Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), being non-ionizing and safe for fetal use while offering detailed structural anatomy, has emerged as a complementary option to USG.

MRI was initially utilized for evaluating the placenta and fetus in 1983, with fetal motion posing a challenge until the development of ultrafast sequences in the 1990s. The Safety Committee of the Society for MRI has not confirmed any biological risks associated with MRI to date, though concerns persist over acoustic noise and potential fetal hearing damage, which remains unconfirmed in practical settings.[2,3] Fetal MRI is recommended when other non-ionizing diagnostic methods are inadequate or when detailed information without exposure to ionizing radiation is crucial. The quality of fetal MRI is comparable to postnatal MRI, enabling

informed discussions regarding potential surgical interventions. [4,5] For optimal results, fetal MRI is ideally conducted in the second or third trimester, post-16 weeks of gestation to ensure the cerebral parenchyma's multilayer structure is adequately appreciable on a 1.5 T MR scanner. Patients are instructed to fast for four hours before the study to reduce bowel artifacts and minimize fetal motion postprandially. They are also advised to empty their bladder prior to the scan and typically positioned feet-first in a supine or left lateral decubitus position.[6]

Case 1:

A 26 yrs old primigravida came to OPD for routine ultrasound examination. She is non-diabetic, non-hypertensive, nonalcoholic, nonsmoker, no family h/o any congenital abnormalities.

On sonography imaging at 28 weeks of gestation shown defect in the anterior abdominal wall size of 1.7cm in which through abnormal herniation of bowel loops seen with external covering membrane. The herniation was in midline.

Figure 1: Sagittal & axial images on sonography imaging at 28 weeks of gestation shown defect in the anterior abdominal wall size of 1.7cm in which through abnormal herniation of bowel loops seen with external covering membrane. The herniation was in midline.

On MRI which was done after one week of usg shown evidence of herniation of few parts of bowel loops seen through a defect in the anterior abdominal wall at root of umbilical cord. The sac is well defined & encapsulated measuring approx. 3.99x3.68 cm.

Figure 2: Sagittal T2WI done after one week of usg shown evidence of herniation of few parts of bowel loops seen through a defect in the anterior abdominal wall at root of umbilical cord. The sac is well defined & encapsulated measuring approx 3.99x3.68 cm.

Diagnosis:

Omphalocele.

D/D:

Pseudo-Omphalocele:

In cases of oligohydramnios, due to uterine pressure, the abdomen elongates in an AP direction and narrows transversely; this gives a spurious appearance of herniated viscera with the umbilical cord and vessels extend into the midline of the pseudo-herniation. Also in abnormal fetal position where the fetal abdomen gets wedged in the uterus

between myometrium and placenta, causing a compression of the fetal abdominal wall even in the absence of oligohydramnios.

Gastroschiasis: Smaller paraumbilical defect usually to the right of midline, usually containing only bowel loops and not covered by a membrane.

Normal physiological midgut herniation:

It usually occurs from around 6-8 weeks until 12-13 weeks in utero, after which the bowel returns to the abdominal cavity.

Case 2:

A 20 yrs old primigravida came to OPD for routine anomaly scan.

She is non-diabetic, non-hypertensive, nonalcoholic, nonsmoker, no family h/o any congenital ab-

normalities. On sonographic imaging at 23 weeks shown bilateral enlarged fetal kidney with dilation of bilateral renal pelvicalyceal of 1.12 cm on right side & 1.0 cm on left side. With normal urinary bladder.

No associated anomaly seen.

Figure 3: Sonographic imaging at 23 weeks shown bilateral enlarged fetal kidney with dilation of bilateral renal pelvicalyceal of 1.12 cm on right side & 1.0 cm on left side. With normal urinary bladder.

On MRI which was done after one week of usg shown evidence of dilatation involving the bilateral renal pelvicalyceal system with right measuring approx 1.23 cm in ap diameter & left measuring approx 1.01cm in ap diameter.

Figure 4: MRI which was done after one week of usg shown evidence of dilatation involving the bilateral renal pelvicalyceal system with right measuring approx 1.23 cm in ap diameter & left measuring approx 1.01cm in ap diameter

Diagnosis:**Bilateral moderate hydronephrosis (Right>left).****D/D:**

Pseudo-hydronephrosis: fluid-density material within a dilated part of the urinary tract, but without other signs of obstruction such as retroperitoneal fat stranding, renal perfusion abnormality, or renal enlargement. Normal anatomical variant.

Extra renal pelvis: Normal anatomical variant. Presence of the renal pelvis outside the confines of the renal hilum. Usually appears dilated.

Cystic renal diseases:

Shows multiple or single well defined thin walled cystic lesion.

Case 3:

An 18 year old primigravida came to OPD for routine anomaly scan. She is nondiabetic, non-hypertensive, nonalcoholic, nonsmoker, no family h/o any congenital abnormalities.

On sonographic imaging at 25 weeks of gestation reveals dilated occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles. Patient was advised for fetal MRI.

Figure 5: Sonographic imaging at 25 weeks of gestation reveals dilated occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles

On MRI evidence of dilated occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles. Corpus callosum could not be visualized properly.

Figure 6: On MRI evidence of dilated occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles.

Diagnosis: Colpocephaly.

Case 4:

A 23 yrs old primigravida on sonographic imaging at 23 weeks shows normally developed upper cerebellum, vermis, normal sized cisterna magna with

evidence of well-defined cystic lesion involving lower part of cerebellum with key hole appearance. Patient was advised for fetal MRI. She came to OPD for routine anomaly scan. She is non diabetic, non-hypertensive, nonalcoholic, nonsmoker, no family h/o any congenital abnormalities.

Figure 7: sonographic imaging at 23 weeks shows normally developed upper cerebellum, vermis, normal sized cisterna magna with evidence of well-defined cystic lesion involving lower part of cerebellum with key hole appearance

MRI reveals a well-defined posterior fossa cystic mass communicating with fourth ventricle with 'keyhole appearance'. Dilated lateral ventricles.

Figure 8: MRI reveals a well-defined posterior fossa cystic mass communicating with fourth ventricle with 'keyhole appearance'. Dilated lateral ventricles.

Diagnosis:**Blake's pouch cyst.**

D/D:

Mega Cisterna Magna:

- Communicates freely with both fourth ventricle and subarachnoid Space
- Other Entities of the Dandy-Walker Continuum:
- Cerebellar Vermis Malformations

Arachnoid Cyst: No hydrocephalus**Case 5:**

An 18 yrs old primigravida came to OPD for routine anomaly scan. She is non diabetic, non-hypertensive, nonalcoholic, nonsmoker, no family h/o any congenital abnormalities.

On sonographic imaging at 24 weeks shows normal developed upper cerebellum, vermis, normal sized cisterna. Splenium of corpus callosum not visualized properly with parallelly placed dilated occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles.

Patient was advised for fetal MRI.

Figure 9: sonographic imaging at 24 weeks shows normal developed upper cerebellum, vermis, normal sized cisterna. Splenium of corpus callosum not visualized properly with parallelly placed dilated occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles

MRI reveals dilated & parallelly placed occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles measuring approx. 1.40 x 1.30cm in diameter & Splenium of corpus callosum not visualized.

Figure 10: MRI reveals dilated & parallelly placed occipital horns of bilateral lateral ventricles measuring approx. 1.40 x 1.30cm in diameter & Splenium of corpus callosum not visualized

Diagnosis:

A single intrauterine gestation with partial agenesis of corpus callosum & bilateral Colpocephaly.

D/D:

In the setting of an antenatal ultrasound demonstrating an interhemispheric cyst then the following should be considered

Cavum vergae: Fluid space enclosed by the leaves of the septum pellucidum with posterior extension beyond the columns of the fornix and foramina of Monro.

Cavum velum interpositi:

An enlarged CSF space situated between the atria/trigones of the lateral ventricles, behind the foramen of Monro, beneath the columns of the fornices with apex pointing anteriorly.

Cavum septi pellucidi:

Located anterior to the foramen of Monro, between the frontal horns of the lateral ventricles also triangular, but with the apex pointing posteriorly.

Inter hemispheric Arachnoid Cyst:

No hydrocephalus

Discussion:

The discussion emphasizes the critical role of routine ultrasound and fetal MRI in accurately diagnosing various prenatal conditions. These imaging techniques allow for detailed visualization of fetal anomalies, enabling precise identification and differentiation from similar conditions. For example, abdominal wall defects like omphalocele can be distinguished from pseudo-omphalocele and gastroschisis. [7,8] Renal abnormalities such as hydronephrosis can be identified, with MRI helping to rule out differentials like pseudo-hydronephrosis and extra renal pelvis. Central nervous system anomalies, including colpocephaly and partial agenesis of the corpus callosum, are detectable, with MRI providing detailed views essential for accurate diagnosis. [9] Accurate prenatal diagnosis aids in planning medical or surgical interventions and preparing healthcare teams for potential complications, while also enabling comprehensive counselling for expectant parents. The integration of these advanced imaging techniques in prenatal care enhances diagnostic accuracy, improves perinatal outcomes, and highlights their transformative impact on managing congenital anomalies, benefiting both mother and fetus. [10]

Conclusion

Ultrasonography remains the primary method for prenatal diagnosis due to its effectiveness, real-time imaging, and established role. As advancements in

prenatal treatment evolve, the importance of precise prenatal diagnosis grows. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) offers notable advantages over ultrasonography, including superior tissue contrast and a broader view of anatomical relationships. MRI is also not affected by maternal obesity or oligohydramnios and is less reliant on operator skill. However, it has limitations, particularly in assessing fetal limbs and detecting cardiac anomalies. Therefore, MRI complements ultrasonography by enhancing diagnostic accuracy and informing treatment and delivery planning. Together, these imaging techniques provide a more comprehensive approach to prenatal care.

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